

**ЗНАЧЕННЯ ЗАСОБІВ ПРИРОДНОГО ПОХОДЖЕННЯ ДЛЯ
ЛІКУВАННЯ ЗАПАЛЬНИХ ПРОЦЕСІВ ПОРОЖНИНИ РОТА,
СПРИЧИНЕНИХ ГРИБКОВИМИ ПАТОГЕНАМИ (ОГЛЯД
ЛІТЕРАТУРИ)**

**THE VALUE OF NATURAL PRODUCTS FOR THE TREATMENT OF
INFLAMMATORY PROCESSES OF THE ORAL CAVITY CAUSED BY
FUNGAL PATHOGENS (REVIEW)**

М. О. Черпак

M. O. Cherpak

ORCID: 0000-0001-7102-0971

Львівський Національний Медичний Університет імені Данила Галицького

Кафедра ортопедичної стоматології

м. Львів, Україна

Danylo Halytsky Lviv National Medical University (LNMU)

Prosthetic Dentistry Department

Lviv, Ukraine

e-mail: cerpakmisa@gmail.com; office@meduniv.lviv.ua

Introduction. Inflammatory processes in the oral cavity are almost always accompanied by significant contamination of various microorganisms and fungi, which in most cases are typical saprophytes of the skin and mucous membranes. In particular, fungal lesions of the oral mucosa are found among stomatology diseases. As is already known, with long-term use of antibiotics, a significant decrease in immunity, when the probability increases of developing oral dysbacteriosis, fungi of the genus *Candida* become pathogenic and can cause clinical mycoses, candidiasis and stomatitis [3].

Purpose of scientific work. Conduct a literature and information search with the analysis of available modern medicines of bionatural (herbal) origin, which are used, or can be used in dental practice for candidiasis and stomatitis.

Materials and methods. Sources of scientific medical literature, materials of internet resources, patent information materials and databases on certain topics.

Results and discussion. It is known that the cause of candidiasis, oral disease and one of the factors in the development of stomatitis and some forms of parodontitis, are fungi of the genus *Candida albicans*. When assessing the kind of sensitivity of drugs to these microorganisms, there is a combination of *Candida albicans* strains with other *Candida* fungi, which complicates the treatment process [4]. Other species of *Candida*, such as *Candida glabrata*, *Candida tropicalis*, *Candida parapsilosis*, and *Candida krusei*, also follow the clinical material in the diseases [5].

The role assigned to herbal medicines in dental practice to eliminate such inflammatory processes and conditions has been determined. Especially with regard to their complex action and spectrum of pharmacological activity. According to many authors, it can be argued that the biologically active compounds of plant origin are

characterized by low toxicity and allergenicity, and can be reduced over time, especially in the case of chronic inflammatory processes [1, 2].

Conclusions. Marketing research shows that the pharmaceutical medical market has a limited number of herbal medicines with complex antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and immunomodulatory activity.

That is why the search, development and complex treatments of candidiasis, stomatitis and parodontitis using polyvalent herbal remedies in various dosage forms is a relevant, timely and promising area of research.

References

1. Перспективи створення нових оригінальних препаратів на основі субстанцій рослинного походження / Р.А.Рубан, С.А.Малиновська, Аль-Товайті Мурад, С.І.Мазурець. Фітотерапія. Часопис. - 2012. - № 2. - С.63-65.

2. Півень О.П. Перспективи створення та виробництва лікарських засобів ноотропної дії із сировини рослинного походження / О.П.Півень, Г.П.Сліпченко // Фармацевтичний журнал. - 2012.- № 4.- С. 23-26.

3. Сахарчук І.І. Антибактеріальна протимікозна терапія у клінічній медицині / І.І.Сахарчук, В.І.Мальцев, Р.І.Ільницький - К.: "Книга плюс", 2004.- 424 с.

4. Dilek S. The antifungal susceptibilities of oral Candida spp. isolates from HIV-infected patients / Dilek Satana, Gonca Erkose Gene and Zayre Erturan //Afr. J. Microbiol. Res. - 2010. - V.4 (6). - P. 466-470.

5. Yuvraj S. Oral candidiasis: a review / Yuvraj Singh Dangi, Murari Lal Soni, Kamta Prasad Namdeo // J. Pharm. and Pharm. Sci. - 2010. - V.2 (4). - P. 36-41.